

125, 561). This observation has also been supported by Dey, Rao and Seshadri (*loc. cit.*), who record "though the use of mercuric acetate resulted in a better yield (of 5-nitrocoumaric acid) the product obtained was rather impure and required several crystallisations."

Incidentally it may also be noted that whereas 6-aminocoumarin produces 6-acetoxymercuriaminocoumarin with mercuric acetate where the mercury atom replaces the hydrogen in the amino group (Sen and Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*) Naik and Patel have obtained 7-amino-6:8-bisacetoxymercuri-4-methylcoumarin from 7-amino-4-methylcoumarin and have given no experimental evidence that the compound possesses a free NH_2 group.

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Received January 28, 1935.

Geometrical Inversion in the Acids Derived from Coumarins (A Note).

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In connection with the paper on the above subject (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 743) it was found necessary to give fuller details of certain experiments and to correct certain errors that had crept in during the course of publication.

7-Methoxycoumarin was obtained in a rather poor yield (1.5 g.) from umbelliferone (4 g.) by methylation in the ordinary way with dimethylsulphate in the presence of caustic alkali. A better yield (2.8 g.) was produced when the methylation was effected in benzene solution (boiling for 2 to 3 hours) in the presence of excess of anhydrous potassium carbonate. The decanted solution was distilled to remove the solvent and the residue was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 117-18°. But the easiest method for preparing the methoxycoumarin was from monomethylresorcinol which was itself made as below:

Resorcinol (11 g.) dissolved in a 10% solution of caustic soda (40 c. c.) was gradually treated at 60-70° with dimethyl sulphate (18 g.) accompanied by vigorous shaking. The reaction was completed by heating on a boiling water-bath for half an hour. The upper layer of oil was separated, the lower aqueous layer twice extracted with ether, the ether extract distilled, the resulting oil added to the main portion and the whole distilled in steam. The distillate was shaken up with ether and the ether solution extracted with 10% aqueous caustic soda. Monomethylresorcinol was thereby taken into the alkaline solution leaving behind in ether any dimethyl ether that might have been formed. The alkaline solution was acidified, ether extracted and the ether solution dried over calcium chloride. The monomethyl ether obtained after removing the solvent was purified by redistillation. It was a colourless liquid with a pleasant smell, boiling at 242-43°, yield 7.5 g. The condensation of the monomethyl ether with malic acid has already been described.

Action of Sunlight on the trans Acids and their Esters.

o-Coumaric acid.—After exposing the alcoholic solution to sunlight, alcohol was distilled off. The residue was dissolved in ether and the ether solution shaken with small quantities of 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate till the aqueous layer became perfectly colourless and nonfluorescent thereby indicating complete removal of all unchanged acid. The ether solution was then washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and finally evaporated in a tared flask. The residue (coumarin) was weighed after drying in an evacuated desiccator over sulphuric acid for 24 hours, yield 65% after 24 hours' exposure and 48% after 6 hours' exposure.

In the case of the esters of *o*-coumaric acid the procedure was the same except that 2% aqueous caustic soda was used for removing unchanged esters from the coumarin formed. Methyl ester underwent 87% conversion in 24 hours and 54% in 6 hours whereas the ethyl ester underwent 74% conversion in 24 hours.

